

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-5-131-IG-5% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	20230620
Vial:	31	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM5130
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	280.0nm
Run Time:	13.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 280.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	6/20/2023 19:59:26 CST		
Date Processed:	6/21/2023 20:18:29 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.056	108597	9.78	11607
2	6.974	439204	39.55	37606
3	8.217	460967	41.51	34716
4	9.796	101842	9.17	6008

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-5-130-IG-5% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230616
Vial:	44	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	5 130
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	280.0nm
Run Time:	13.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 280.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	6/16/2023 9:37:42 PM CST		
Date Processed:	6/21/2023 8:31:09 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.411	39516	1.32	4220
2	7.365	2924415	97.83	242961
3	8.740	14737	0.49	1184
4	10.480	10470	0.35	625